

A New Perspective on Galactic Dynamics: Decreasing Galaxy Rotation Curves

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Abstract : This paper proposes a bold revision of classical galactic dynamics models, drawing inspiration from the structure of the solar system. Confronting the limitations of current theories, which fail to explain the flat rotation curves of galaxies according to Kepler's laws and generalized Newtonian gravitation, we introduce a new model where a giant elliptical galaxy occupies a central position, surrounded by non-active galaxies in orbit, forming a coherent galactic system. By applying this model to real systems centered on the giant elliptical galaxies M87, M60, and NGC 1399 (chosen arbitrarily), we observed decreasing rotation curves, consistent with Keplerian predictions, and determined gravitational constants specific to each system. These findings open new perspectives in understanding galactic dynamics and could provide alternative solutions to the mysteries surrounding dark matter.

Keywords: Galactic dynamics, Decreasing rotation curves, Giant elliptical galaxy, Keplerian model, Gravitational constants, Galactic system

1. INTRODUCTION

The observation of galaxy rotation curves has long been a persistent enigma for astronomers. According to the predictions of generalized Newtonian gravitation, one would expect the rotational velocity of stars and gas within a galaxy to decrease with distance from the center. However, observations often reveal rotation curves that remain relatively flat even at the edges of galaxies, thereby challenging theoretical expectations. This discrepancy between observations and predictions of the classical gravitational model constitutes a significant challenge to our understanding of galactic dynamics.

The scientific literature is abundant with theories and models aimed at explaining galaxy rotation curves. Among these, the dark matter theory is widely accepted [1-5], postulating the existence of an invisible form of matter that interacts gravitationally with ordinary matter. However, despite decades of intensive research, no direct evidence of the existence of dark matter has yet been obtained. Furthermore, alternative theories have emerged [6-11], questioning the need to invoke dark matter to explain galactic observations, such as large-scale modifications to gravity.

In this study, we propose to challenge the existing models used to explain galaxy rotation curves. Our goal is to offer an innovative and coherent approach, based on the solar system model, to better understand these astrophysical phenomena. By applying generalized Newtonian gravitation to our proposed model, taking into account the gravitational constant G , we obtained decreasing rotation curves, consistent with the theoretical expectations of the classical model. This approach could open new perspectives in our understanding of galactic dynamics and provide alternative solutions to the mysteries of dark matter.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

In the field of physics, the study of gravity has always been central to efforts aimed at understanding the forces that shape the Universe on a large scale. Two fundamental theories stand out as essential pillars in this quest: classical gravity, formulated by Sir Isaac Newton in the 17th century, and Albert Einstein's general relativity, which redefined our understanding of gravity in the 20th century. The generalised Newton's law of gravitation, expressed in equation (1), has been fundamental in explaining planetary motions within our solar system and the gravitational interactions between celestial bodies. However, it applies primarily in weak gravitational fields and at low speeds.

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{GM(r)}{r}} \quad (1)$$

However, on a large scale, the limitations of classical gravity become apparent, and Einstein's general relativity takes over. This theory redefines gravity as the curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy, providing a more complete understanding of stellar motions and galactic rotation curves. By combining Newton's laws with the principles of general relativity, a robust theoretical framework is established to explore gravity at all cosmic scales, from planetary systems to vast galactic structures.

3. METHODOLOGY

The flat rotation curves of galaxies (Figure 1) [12], [13], obtained from various observations, reveal the relationship between the velocity and the distance of stars from the galactic center. They show that stars in the galactic disk maintain an almost constant velocity, regardless of their distance from the central bulge of the galaxy, in contrast to the decreasing velocity curves of planets around the Sun, where velocity decreases with distance according to Kepler's third law.

Fig. 1. Rotation curve of a typical spiral galaxy: theoretical prediction (A) and actual observation (B) [12], [13].

For planets, each orbits the Sun individually with its own angular and orbital velocity, distinct from those of other planets. In contrast, in a rotating galaxy, stars do not move individually but accompany the rotation of the galactic disk with the same angular velocity.

This highlights two distinct models: in planetary systems, objects orbit individually around a central body with varying angular velocities, whereas in galaxies, stars move in synchronization with the galactic disk. Thus, all stars in the galactic disk share the same angular velocity and do not follow Kepler's third law.

To better illustrate the differences between the two models, we have established Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison table of the two models

Characteristics	1st Model: Planetary gravitation model	2nd Model: Galaxy rotation model
Motion	Each planet follows its own gravitational motion around the Sun.	Stars do not have distinct individual orbits like planets but follow the overall rotational motion of the galactic disk.
Angular velocity	Planets in the solar system have different angular velocities.	All stars within a galaxy share the same angular velocity.
Center of rotation	The Sun, around which the planets orbit, is a distinct body, separate from other objects in the solar system.	The galactic bulge, regarded as the center of rotation, along with the stars in the galaxy, constitutes a unified structure.

Table 1 highlights the difference between the planetary gravitation model, where planets orbit around the Sun, and the galaxy rotation model used to plot rotation curves. In the first model, distinct objects orbit around a central body, the Sun, whereas in the second model, the rotation involves a single body, the galaxy. These two concepts are fundamentally different, leading to distinct results when applying the generalized Newton's law (Equation 1). This divergence explains the flat rotation curves observed in galaxies. Given this distinction, the galaxy rotation model cannot conform to the generalized Newton's law and does not apply to Kepler's third law.

4. PRESENTATION OF THE NEW MODEL

Based on the criteria outlined below, we propose a new model, adapted from the solar system model, to plot the rotation curves of galaxies.

1. Confirmed presence of giant elliptical galaxies at the center of a galaxy group, as observed in references [14-16].
2. Significant gravitational influence exerted by these giant ellipticals on the other galaxies in their group.
3. The considerably greater mass of giant ellipticals compared to the surrounding galaxies.
4. The imposing size of giant ellipticals, surpassing that of other types of surrounding galaxies.

Based on these criteria and the reference article [17], which suggests that active giant elliptical galaxies play a role similar to that of stars on an extragalactic scale, we have developed a new model. This model, inspired by the solar system, is extended to the galactic scale. We draw an analogy: a massive and imposing giant elliptical galaxy occupies the center, while non-active galaxies orbit around it, each following its own orbit, thus forming a galactic system (Figure 2). To ensure consistency with the solar system, the galaxies within each galactic system must be coplanar or approximately coplanar with their central giant elliptical galaxy, just as planets are with the Sun. We then plot the curve for each galactic system that represents the velocity of the galaxies, considered as orbital velocity, as a function of their distance from the central giant elliptical galaxy.

Fig. 2. The proposed model of a galactic system with dynamics analogous to the solar system.

5. GALAXY ROTATION CURVES FROM THE NEW MODEL

In this study, we have selected three giant elliptical galaxies that play a crucial role in their respective galaxy clusters. The chosen galaxies are: NGC 4486 (M87) and NGC 4649 (M60), two prominent members of the Virgo Cluster, as well as NGC 1399, which is also a dominant member of the Fornax Cluster.

These elliptical galaxies share several common characteristics: they are all supergiants with substantial masses, exhibit very low absolute magnitudes, possess active nuclei, and each occupies the center of a galaxy group.

To plot the rotation curves associated with these three galaxies, it is necessary to identify the galaxies that form the galactic systems surrounding each of these giant ellipticals. The galaxies forming these systems must meet the following criteria:

1. They are non-active galaxies.
2. They belong to the group of the giant elliptical galaxy.
3. They are located in the vicinity of the giant elliptical galaxy and are centered around it.
4. They are coplanar or approximately coplanar with their central giant elliptical galaxy.

5.1 Method used to plot galactic system rotation curves

To plot the galactic system rotation curves, we first considered the velocity of each member galaxy of a galactic system as an orbital velocity around the central elliptical galaxy. We then established the curve representing the orbital velocity of each galaxy as a function of its distance from the central galaxy.

Initially, we need to extract all the necessary data from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [18] to:

1. Calculate the distance D_{1-2} between the central elliptical galaxy and each member of its galactic system.
2. Ensure that all members exhibit the same gravitational constant, calculated based on the generalized Newtonian law.
3. Verify the coplanarity of the members of each galactic system.

5.2 Selection the of member galaxies for each galactic system

To select the member galaxies of the galactic system centered on one of the giant ellipticals NGC 4486 (M87), NGC 4649 (M60), or NGC 1399, we used multiple data sources. On one hand, we referred to the group listings of these giants from the catalogs of Henry Ferguson [19], Abraham Mahtessian, and A.M. García [20], [21]. On the other hand, we searched for the list of surrounding galaxies for each of these giant elliptical galaxies via the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (Radial Velocity Constrained Cone Searches) [22] by entering the specific data of these giant galaxies, including the Hubble constant ($H_0 = 67.8$ km/s/Mpc), matter density ($\Omega_{\text{matter}} = 0.308$), and vacuum energy density, or cosmological constant ($\Omega_{\text{vacuum}} = 0.692$). We also entered the redshift-independent metric distance for each galaxy to determine the search cone opening angle, adjusted to a maximum radius of 10 Mpc at the specified distance, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. View of the search cone around the galaxies NGC 4486, NGC 4649, and NGC 1399. based on radial data from NASA/IPAC [22].

5.3 Calculation of the distance between the giant elliptical galaxy and its members

In each galactic system, the distance D_{1-2} separating the central elliptical galaxy from each of its members is calculated using equation (2).

$$D_{1-2} = \sqrt{D_1^2 + D_2^2 - 2D_1 D_2 \cos \theta} \quad (2)$$

Where

D_1 : Hubble distance (corrected by the CMB) separating the giant elliptical galaxy from the Earth.

D_2 : Hubble distance (corrected by the CMB) separating the galaxy member of the galactic system from the Earth.

θ : The angle formed by the two unit vectors $\vec{r}_1$ and $\vec{r}_2$, calculated using equation (3).

$$\theta = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{\vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_2}{|\vec{r}_1| \cdot |\vec{r}_2|} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where $\vec{r}_1$ and $\vec{r}_2$ expressed by relations (4) and (5) are the unit vectors pointing from Earth toward the direction of the two galaxies.

$$\vec{r}_1 = (\sin(\delta_1), \cos(\delta_1) \cos(\alpha_1), \cos(\delta_1) \sin(\alpha_1)) \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{r}_2 = (\sin(\delta_2), \cos(\delta_2) \cos(\alpha_2), \cos(\delta_2) \sin(\alpha_2)) \quad (5)$$

δ and α are respectively the declination and right ascension, which represent the equatorial coordinates of the galaxies converted to degrees.

And $\vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_2$ is the dot product between the two vectors $\vec{r}_1$ and $\vec{r}_2$

5.4. Calculation of the gravitational constant

The gravitational constant G is the final parameter that needs to be defined to validate the choice of the selected list of galaxies. The constant G is calculated using relation (6) derived from relation (1).

$$G = \frac{v^2 \cdot D_{1-2}}{M_{Ge}} \quad (6)$$

v is the velocity of the galaxies within the system, considered as the orbital velocity.

M_{Ge} is the mass of the central elliptical galaxy.

5.5. The Coplanarity of galaxies within the same galactic system

To verify the approximate coplanarity of several galaxies, various methods can be employed by combining astronomical tools with geometric concepts. The approach we used is based on the following steps:

- **Conversion of equatorial coordinates:** The equatorial coordinates of the galaxies, defined by right ascension (α), declination (δ), and distance (d), are converted into Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) using the following relations:

$$x = d \cdot \cos(\delta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)$$

$$y = d \cdot \cos(\delta) \cdot \sin(\alpha)$$

$$z = d \cdot \sin(\delta)$$

- **Fitting a plane:** Once the Cartesian coordinates are calculated, a plane is defined by considering the central elliptical galaxy and two other galaxies arbitrarily chosen from the studied list. This plane is described by the equation $ax + by + cz + d = 0$.

Where a, b, c and d are real constants.

- **Analysis of deviations from the plane:** After defining the equation of the plane, the distance from the plane of each galaxy with Cartesian coordinates (x_1, y_1, z_1) is calculated using relation 7. Galaxies with very small distances from the plane are considered approximately coplanar.

$$d = \frac{|ax_1 + by_1 + cz_1|}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2}} \quad (7)$$

6. APPLICATION OF THE NEW MODEL

We apply our new model to the galactic systems centered around three giant elliptical galaxies: NGC 4486 (M87), NGC 4649 (M60), and NGC 1399, in order to plot the rotation curves of this galactic systems,

To do this, we considered the velocity of each galaxy within the galactic system as an orbital velocity around the central elliptical galaxy of this system.

The NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [18] provides two measurements for each galaxy: the heliocentric velocity (Helio) and the velocity relative to the cosmic microwave background (CMB). Since our model focuses on the large-scale dynamics of galaxies, the CMB velocity is the most appropriate. It offers a comprehensive view of the movement of galaxies within the global context of the Universe.

6.1. Rotation curve for the M87 galactic system

6.1.1. Overview of the M87 galaxy

M87 (Messier 87) or NGC 4486 is a supergiant elliptical radio galaxy located at 15.4 ± 0.6 Mpc (~ 50.2 million light-years) [23] in the Virgo Cluster. It is the largest and brightest galaxy in the Virgo Cluster [24], [25]. At its core lies a supermassive black hole, the central feature of an active galactic nucleus, which is a strong source of radiation across all wavelengths, particularly in microwaves. A jet of energetic plasma emerges from the core and extends for at least 5,000 light-years [26]. M87 has a photometric mass of $3.6 \times 10^{11} M_{\odot}$, corresponding to a mass of 7.16×10^{41} kg. Its massive size and central position make it an intriguing subject for our research.

6.1.2. Selection of the surrounding members of the giant elliptical galaxy M87

The members of the galactic system centered on the giant elliptical galaxy M87 were selected from two sources: the M87 group lists from the catalogs of Abraham Mahtessian and A.M. García [20], [21], and the list obtained through a search conducted in the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (Radial Velocity Constrained Cone Searches) [22]. From these lists, we chose non-active galaxies that are approximately coplanar with M87 and whose gravitational constants are approximately equal.

The selected members of the M87 galactic system, along with their astronomical coordinates and velocities relative to the cosmic microwave background (CMB) extracted from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [18], are presented in Table 2. In this table, the Hubble

distances show the distance D_1 between the galaxy M87 and Earth (23.79 ± 1.70 Mpc), as well as the distances D_2 separating Earth from the other galaxies.

Table 2: Equatorial Coordinates and CMB velocities for the member galaxies of the M87 galactic system.

Galaxy name	α	δ	Hubble distance (CMB) [Mpc]
M87	187.705930	12.391123	23.79 +/- 1.70
NGC 4477	187.509159	13.636604	24.55 $\pm$ 1.75
VPC 0766	187.693292	12.099083	23.52 $\pm$ 1.68
VCC 1313	187.702175	12.045016	23.38 $\pm$ 1.67
VCC 1307	187.685917	13.799444	23.11 $\pm$ 1.89
NGC 4459	187.250037	13.978373	22.40 $\pm$ 1.61
NGC 4497	187.88553	11.624718	20.24 $\pm$ 1.46
NGC 4488	187.71406	8.359994	19.42 $\pm$ 1.40
NGC 4483	187.669357	9.015678	17.98 $\pm$ 1.31
VCCA 038	187.51092	9.403306	18.21 $\pm$ 1.35

By applying the data from table 2 into equations (2), (3), (4), (5), and (6), we calculated the distance D_{1-2} separating the galaxy M87 from each member of its galactic system, as well as the gravitational constants. The results presented in Table 3 show approximately equal gravitational constants, ranging from $2.0493 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$ to $2.703 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$. The average gravitational constant G is $2.28387 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$.

The calculated gravitational constants exhibit values that are approximately equal, but not strictly identical. This is due to the fact that the CMB velocities of the galaxies and the Hubble distances (CMB) separating them from Earth, obtained from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [18], are approximate measurements rather than exact values. These slight variations in the input data result in minor differences in the calculated gravitational constants.

Table 3: Calculated Values of distances D_{1-2} and the gravitational constant G for the M87 galactic system.

Galaxy name	CMB velocity (Km/s)	Distance D_{1-2} (Mpc)	Gravitational Constant G ($m^3kg^{-1} s^{-1}$)
NGC 4477	1665 ± 23	17.4591868	2.0859E-06
VPC 0766	1595 ± 23	18.6913504	2.0493E-06
VCC 1313	1585 ± 23	19.8005752	2.1437E-06
VCC 1307	1567 ± 50	20.1617199	2.1336E-06
NGC 4459	1518 ± 23	23.8650693	2.37E-06
NGC 4497	1372 ± 23	26.7226738	2.1678E-06
NGC 4488	1317 ± 24	33.0355691	2.4694E-06
NGC 4483	1219 ± 24	38.8894348	2.5895E-06
VCCA 038	1235 ± 27	41.1224718	2.703E-06

To validate this list, it is necessary to check the approximate coplanarity of the selected galaxies. With this in mind, we first defined the equation of a plane (P1) that includes the central galaxy M87, along with two other galaxies, NGC 4477 and VPC 0766, which were randomly chosen from the list of galaxies in Table 2. The calculations resulted in the following equation: $-0.02487x + 0.05098y - 0.02268z = -0.298$. Subsequently, we determined the distance of the other galaxies in the list relative to this plane, with the results summarized in Table 4.

Table4 : Distances of the selected galaxies from the plane (P1).

Galaxy name	VCC 1313	VCC 1307	NGC 4459	NGC 4497	NGC 4488	NGC 4483	VCCA 038
Distance (Mpc)	0.022	0.375	0.398	0.667	0.327	0.737	0.691

The results show that the distances of these galaxies from the plane (P1) with the equation $-0.02487x + 0.05098y - 0.02268z = -0.298$ vary from 0.022 Mpc to 0.737 Mpc, with a maximum deviation of 0.737 Mpc. Since these deviations are relatively small on a cosmic scale (less than 1 Mpc), it can be concluded that these galaxies, as well as M87, VCC 4477, and VPC 0766, are approximately coplanar.

After finalizing the list of galaxies in the M87 galactic system, we used Excel to plot the curve shown in Figure 4. This curve illustrates the CMB velocities of the galaxies in the system as a function of their distance from the central galaxy, M87. We consider the CMB velocities of these galaxies as their orbital velocities

Fig. 4. Rotation curve for the M87 galactic system

6.1.3. Interpretation of results

The curve in Figure 4 shows that the non-active galaxies in the galactic system centered on the giant M87, which are approximately coplanar with it, follow a decreasing curve consistent with Kepler's law and the generalized law of Newtonian gravitation.

6.2. Rotation curve for the M60 galactic system

6.2.1. Presentation of the galaxy M60 (NGC 4649)

M60, also known as NGC 4649, is the third brightest giant elliptical galaxy in the Virgo Cluster. According to the latest data from reference [18], it is located at a distance of 16.702 ± 3.449 Mpc (approximately 54.5 million light-years). The central bulge of NGC 4649 hosts a supermassive black hole [27] [28]. As a radio galaxy, NGC 4649 also has an active nucleus and two lobes extending to the northeast and southwest, along an axis oriented approximately 31° east of north [30]. Its massive size and central position within a group of galaxies make it a particularly interesting subject of study for our research.

6.2.2. Selection of the surrounding members of the giant elliptical galaxy M60

The selection of the galaxies surrounding the giant elliptical galaxy NGC 4649 (M60), which form its galactic system, was made from two sources: the M60 group list from the catalogs of Abraham Mahtessian and A.M. García [20], [21], and the list of nearby galaxies list obtained through a search conducted in the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (Radial Velocity Constrained Cone Searches) [22]. The selected galaxies must be non-active, approximately coplanar with M60, and have gravitational constants that are equal or approximately equal.

Table 5 presents the equatorial coordinates and velocities (CMB) of the galaxy M60, along with those of the selected members of its galactic system, extracted from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [18]. In this table, the Hubble distances illustrate the distance D_1 from Earth to the galaxy M60 (21.14 ± 1.52 Mpc) and the distances D_2 between Earth and the other galaxies.

Table 5 : Equatorial coordinates and CMB velocities for the member galaxies of the M60 galactic system.

Galaxy name	α	δ	Hubble distance (CMB) [Mpc]
M60	190.916564	11.552706	21.14 +/- 1.52
NGC 4635	190.663503	19.945312	18.59 +/- 1.34
NGC 4600	190.095664	3.117750	17.32 +/- 1.26
VCC 1950	190.751479	16.087184	16.02 +/- 1.20
NGC 4651	190.927625	16.393389	16.41 +/- 1.19
NGC 4630	190.629706	3.960245	15.89 +/- 1.16
VCC 1839	190.108008	4.050149	15.70 +/- 1.28

The distances D_{1-2} between the giant elliptical galaxy M60 and each member of its galactic system, as well as their gravitational constants, are calculated using the data from Table 5 in equations (2), (3), (4), (5), and (6). The results summarized in Table 6 show gravitational constants ranging from $2.2016 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$ to $2.62775 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$. The average gravitational constant G is $2.395783 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$. We also note that the calculated gravitational constants are similar but not perfectly identical. This slight difference is due to the fact that the CMB velocities of the galaxies and their Hubble distances (corrected by the CMB) relative to the Earth, obtained from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database, are approximate values. These variations in the data lead to small discrepancies in the resulting constants.

Table 6: Calculated values of distances D_{1-2} and the constant G for the M60 galactic system.

Galaxy name	CMB velocity (Km/s)	Distance D_{1-2} (Mpc)	Gravitational constant G ($\text{m}^3\text{kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
NGC 4635	1260 +/- 21	19.5769813	2.2943E-06
NGC 4600	1174 +/- 24	21.63879	2.2016E-06
VCC 1950	1086 +/- 26	24.2527156	2.2138E-06
NGC 4651	1113 +/- 22	28.3720528	2.4929E-06
NGC 4630	1077 +/- 24	29.7154869	2.5444E-06
VCC 1839	1064 +/- 36	31.4432391	2.6277E-06

To validate this list, it is essential to verify the approximate coplanarity of the selected galaxies. We began by determining the equation of a plane (P2) passing through the central galaxy M60 and two other galaxies, VCC 1950 and NGC 4630. These two galaxies were arbitrarily chosen from the list of selected galaxies in table5. The resulting equation is as follows: $-3.50x+17.33y+0.21z-4.09=0$. Next, we calculated the distances of the other listed galaxies from this plane, and the results are shown in Table 7.

Table7 : Distances of selected galaxies from the plane (P2)

Galaxy name	VCC 1950	NGC 4651	NGC 4630	VCC 1839
Distance (Mpc)	0.073	0.179	0.042	0.140

The results in Table 7 show that the distances of these galaxies from the plane (P2), with the equation $-3.50x+17.33y+0.21z-4.09=0$, range from 0.042 Mpc to 0.179 Mpc, with a maximum difference of 0.179 Mpc. Given that these variations are relatively small on a cosmic scale (less than 1 Mpc), we can conclude that these galaxies, along with M60, VCC 1950, and NGC 4630, are approximately coplanar.

With the list of galaxies in the M60 galactic system finalized, we moved on to the simulation. Using Excel simulation software, we plotted the curve shown in Figure 5. This curve illustrates the CMB velocities of the member galaxies in the M60 system, considered as their orbital velocities, plotted against their distance from the central elliptical galaxy, M60.

Fig. 5. Rotation curve for the M60 galactic system

6.2.3. Interpretation of results

Figure 5 shows that the velocity of the member galaxies of the M60 galactic system decreases as their distance from the central elliptical galaxy M60 increases. This relationship gives a decreasing curve, consistent with Kepler's Third Law and the generalized law of Newtonian gravitation.

6.3. Rotation curve for the NGC 1399 galactic system

3.3.1. Presentation of the galaxy NGC 1399

The radio galaxy NGC 1399 is a giant elliptical galaxy of type E0 [31], located approximately 17.711 ± 0.395 Mpc (about 66 million light-years) from Earth, according to the latest data from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [18]. As the central and dominant member of the Fornax cluster [29], NGC 1399 stands out as one of the brightest galaxies in this cluster, emitting a significant amount of radiation across various wavelengths. Its active nucleus hosts a supermassive black hole [27], [30]. This galaxy, classified as Seyfert 2, features two antiparallel jets, which merge with diffuse lobes [31]. Its central position in the Fornax cluster and its intense activity make it a key target for studying the dynamics and evolution of galaxies within clusters.

6.3.2. Selection of the surrounding members of the giant elliptical NGC 1399

The galaxies surrounding the giant elliptical galaxy NGC 1399, which form its galactic system, were selected from two sources: the Henry Ferguson catalog [19] and the list obtained through a search conducted in the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (cone searches with radial velocity constraints) [22]. The selected galaxies must be non-active, approximately coplanar, and exhibit nearly identical gravitational constants.

The data collected from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [18] for the galaxy NGC 1399 and the members chosen to form its galactic system are compiled in Table 8.

Table 8: Equatorial coordinates and CMB velocity for the member galaxies of the NGC 1399 galactic system.

Galaxy name	α	δ	Hubble distance (CMB) [Mpc]
NGC 1399	54.620941	-35.450657	19.65 ± 1.38
ESO 548- G 063	54.894917	-20.014806	27.54 ± 1.94
NGC 1377	54.162833	-20.902250	24.61 ± 1.84
NGC 1369	54.188542	-36.256222	19.48 ± 1.41
IC 1970	54.131333	-43.956833	17.21 ± 1.21
NGC 1406	54.847083	-31.321417	14.37 ± 1.01

The distances D_{1-2} between NGC 1399 and the members of its galactic system, as well as the gravitational constants were, calculated using the data from Table 8 and equations (2), (3), (4),

(5), and (6). The gravitational constants calculated for this system range from $1.02573 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $1.4492 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, with an average value of $1.257834 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The results are compiled in Table 9. The calculated gravitational constants are close but not identical, due to the approximate measurements of the CMB velocities of the galaxies and the Hubble distances (corrected by the CMB) relative to the Earth, provided by the NASA/IPAC website. These variations in the input data cause slight differences in the resulting constants.

Table 9: Calculated values of distances D_{1-2} and the constant G for the NGC 1399 galactic system.

Galaxy name	CMB velocity (Km/s)	Distance D_{1-2} (Mpc)	Gravitational constant G ($\text{m}^3\text{kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
ESO 548- G 063	1868 ± 13	11.190094	1.41916E-06
NGC 1377	1669 ± 31	14.31431352	1.44919E-06
NGC 1369	1321 ± 18	15.7409571	1.02573E-06
IC 1970	1167 ± 7	25.34644547	1.25459E-06
NGC 1406	974 ± 8	33.077567	1.1405E-06

To confirm the validity of this list, it is crucial to verify the approximate coplanarity of the selected galaxies. We began by establishing the equation of a plane (P3) that passes through the central galaxy NGC 1399, along with two other galaxies, NGC 1406 and IC 1970, which were randomly chosen from the list of selected galaxies in Table 8. The following equation was obtained: $0.77x - 0.55y + 0.03z + 0.32 = 0$. Next, we calculated the distances of the other listed galaxies from this plane, and the results are presented in Table 10.

Table10 : Distances of the selected galaxies from the plane (P3)

Galaxy name	NGC 1377	NGC 1369	ESO 548-G 063
Distance (Mpc)	0.184	0.037	0.150

The distances given in table 10 are relatively small compared to intergalactic distances, suggesting that these galaxies, along with NGC 1399, NGC 1406, and IC 1970, are approximately coplanar. Since the approximate coplanarity of the galaxies presented in Table 9 is confirmed, we can use the data from this table to plot the curve shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Rotation curve for the NGC 1399 galactic system

6.3.3. Interpretation of results

Figure 6 presents the velocity curve of the galaxies in the NGC 1399 system, based on their CMB velocities, which are interpreted as their orbital velocities, plotted against their distance from the central galaxy, NGC 1399. This decreasing curve aligns closely with Kepler's law and the generalized Newtonian gravitational law, using an average gravitational constant G of $1.257834 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

6.4. Overall interpretation of results

The rotation curves for the galactic systems centered on the giant elliptical galaxies NGC 4486 (M87), NGC 4349 (M60), and NGC 1399, all of which meet the criteria for a radio galaxy, show a decreasing trend consistent with Kepler's third law and Newton's generalized law of gravitation. The previously plotted graphs highlight the presence of galactic systems, each consisting of an active giant elliptical galaxy surrounded by non-active galaxies, all influenced by the gravitational pull of the central galaxy. By applying equation (6), derived from Newton's generalized law of gravitation, to the non-active galaxies, we found that the gravitational constants of the galaxies within the same system are very similar. This slight variation in gravitational constants can be explained by the fact that the CMB velocities and Hubble distances (adjusted for the CMB) of the galaxies, obtained from the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database [18], are approximate values.

This observation indicates that, within a galactic system, the velocity of each galaxy is determined by its distance from the central giant elliptical radio galaxy.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the innovative approach we have proposed in this paper challenges traditional paradigms of galactic dynamics by offering a new perspective inspired by the solar system model. Unlike current models that struggle to explain galactic rotation curves using Kepler's and Newton's gravitational laws, our model demonstrates consistency with these fundamental laws. By scaling the structure of the solar system to the galactic level, we have shown that systems centered around giant elliptical radio galaxies, such as NGC 4486 (M87), NGC 4649 (M60), and NGC 1399, follow decreasing rotational curves, in agreement with theoretical predictions. This discovery, coupled with the determination of specific gravitational constants for each system, suggests that the dynamics of galaxies may be governed by more universal principles than current models imply.

Beyond its theoretical implications, our model offers new avenues for interpreting galactic phenomena, potentially shedding light on the mysteries of dark matter and redefining our overall understanding of galactic dynamics. Future observational data and simulations could further validate our findings and refine the gravitational constants, paving the way for a broader revision of existing theories. Ultimately, this work opens new horizons for understanding the large-scale structure and evolution of the Universe, positioning it as a significant step forward in the field of cosmology.

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